

DESIGN AND AESTHETICS IN CREATING HARMONIOUS URBAN SPACES (using street litter bins as an example)

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Abstract. *The article examines the state of the architectural environment today and what measures should be taken to avoid pollution, as well as the role of litter bins in this.*

Keywords: *landscape, outdoor environment, household waste, garbage, litter bins.*

Introduction

Street litter bins play an important role in maintaining cleanliness and order in urban spaces. However, in addition to their primary function, litter bins can also make an aesthetic contribution to the urban environment. In this article, we will look at how the design and aesthetics of street litter bins can contribute to the creation of harmonious urban spaces.

1. Integration with the environment: Waste bins can be designed to blend in with the architecture and surrounding landscape. For example, retro-style bins can be a great addition to historic areas, while modern glass bins can blend in beautifully with contemporary buildings.

2. Aesthetics and design: Street bins can be designed in a variety of styles and shapes to match the overall design of the urban environment. They can have interesting geometric shapes, original color schemes or decorative elements. This approach allows not only to provide a functional place for throwing out garbage, but also to create visual interest for residents and visitors of the city.

3. Using litter bins as art objects: Some cities and architects are treating street litter bins as art objects. They invite artists and designers to create litter bins with unique designs or sculptures. This practice helps transform ordinary litter bins into works of art and draws attention to the problem of trash in cities [1].

Street litter bins are an integral part of urban infrastructure. They not only perform an important function of waste collection, but can also be an element of design and aesthetics in the urban environment. The design of litter bins can be integrated with the environment, have original shapes and colors, and also serve as art objects [3]. This approach allows for the creation of harmonious and attractive urban spaces that will be pleasant for residents and visitors of the city.

In general, environmental design is the improvement of a place where a person lives. This can be an apartment, office and public spaces, such as an airport, train station, theater, etc., or a plot in front of a house, in the courtyard of offices or enterprises, the territory of public buildings [2]. The second option is a type of outdoor environmental design. It is usually designed by landscape designers and architects, who take into account many nuances when designing.

Recently, the appearance of cities has been changing very quickly, which is due to the following:

Rapid growth of cities.

A sharp increase in car traffic.

Pollution of the urban environment (figure-1).

Figure-1. Problems in the design of architectural environments

We are used to seeing only beautiful spaces around us, such as these clean beaches, shores, mountains... (figure-2).

Figure-2. beautiful city space

Many find it easier not to notice than to contribute to the action of collecting and eliminating garbage and, unfortunately, today we increasingly encounter natural - beautiful landscapes, disfigured by people. We see waste from human life, which accumulate in tons for half a century or more [5].

Household waste (consumer waste) can be in both solid and liquid, and less often in gaseous form. Solid household waste is the remains that we throw out of houses, institutions, offices and usually call garbage (food waste, plastic, paper, glass, leather, etc.).

Their number increases annually due to population growth and improvements in the quality of life of people (for example, packaging for goods, including those made of polymeric materials, aluminum cans, etc.). Liquid waste is mainly represented by household wastewater, gaseous waste is represented by emissions of various gases. "Plastic waste is splashed onto the beaches of Indonesia, settles on the bottom of the Arctic Ocean and gets through the food chain onto our plates," report experts from the United Nations Environment Program (UNEP) [4].

In 1950, the world's population of 2.5 billion people produced 1.5 million tons of plastic. In 2020, the planet's population exceeded 7 billion people, and the amount of plastic reached 300 million tons, which had devastating consequences for marine plants and animals [6].

If people don't stop using single-use plastics like plastic bags and plastic bottles, there will be more plastic in the world's oceans than fish by 2050 (figure-3).

Dutchman Tommy Klein, getting to his work by bike, rode past a terribly littered beach every day. At some point, he simply took the initiative into his own hands - and began collecting a bag of garbage every day. No, it wasn't his garbage, and no, no one forced him - he just did it, thus setting an excellent example for others.

Figure-3. Ocean Pollution

From this it should be understood that before creating a landscape design of the external environment, it is necessary to consider the number of people and the amount of waste they throw out. When creating a beautiful landscape, it is necessary to put garbage bins in parallel and necessarily for different materials separately [7].

Also, you can use convenient, lightweight and multifunctional large-sized garbage containers in places where a large number of people accumulate, such as stadiums, circuses, amusement parks, concert halls or cinemas.

Such containers can be three compartments in one container or three different containers separately (figure-4).

Figure-4. Street litter bins

The Importance of Street litter bins in the Urban Environment. Street litter bins serve as an important element for collecting and disposing of waste, helping to maintain cleanliness and order on the streets. However, their importance is not limited to functionality alone. The design of bins can contribute to the formation of a characteristic style of the urban environment and create harmony with architectural features.

Innovative design for functionality and aesthetics. Modern street litter bins offer a wide range of design solutions, combining functionality with aesthetic aspects. The design of the bins can be adapted to the style and character of the city, emphasizing its uniqueness. From minimalist and modern forms to classic and artificially aged, the design of street bins can add a special accent to the urban landscape [8].

Innovative materials and technologies also play a role in creating bins with high functionality and durability. Engineers and designers are working on developing materials that are resistant to aggressive environmental influences and are also able to withstand different

weather conditions. The result is bins that retain their appearance and effectiveness for a long time.

Functionality and ease of use. The main purpose of street bins is to provide an effective waste collection system in the urban environment. To do this, they must be easy to use for both citizens and cleaners. It is important to ensure that the bins are correctly located so that they are accessible and visible, eliminating the possibility of accidental dumping of waste near them.

Modern street litter bins can be equipped with separate compartments for different types of waste: plastic bottles, paper, food waste, etc (figure-5). This promotes more efficient recycling and disposal of waste, reduces the negative impact on the environment and promotes the development of a sustainable environmental culture.

Figure-5. Modern street litter bins

Conclusion. The production of street litter bins is an important part of urban infrastructure that must be performed with high quality standards. The production of street litter bins is an important part of urban infrastructure. Street litter bins must be made of durable and long-lasting materials to ensure safety and durability. They must be designed in such a way that they are convenient to use and attractive to citizens.

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